

Business Incubator's Success Factors : Scale Development and Refinement

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Abstract : *Business incubators/incubation centers have been recognized globally in fostering innovation and developing entrepreneurial ecosystem. They have evolved as highly efficient systems for the economic development of industrialized nations. This study tries to identify the measures of incubation performance and further delves into developing a research instrument comprising measures of Business incubator performance. From the literature it was found that the role of networking is critical and influences business incubator performance, other factors such as University linkage and incubation facilities provided to the startup firms also play an important role as far as business incubator performance is concerned. Further, research scale was refined and tests for reliability and validity were performed through CFA for assessing the measurement model, where scales were found unidimensional. The present study thus develops a conceptual model and a research instrument that would help managers in executing their functions by focusing on these critical areas for the enhancement of business incubator performance.*

Keywords : Business Incubators, Entrepreneurship, Startup, University Linkages, Networking.

1. Introduction

Every country tries to focus on knowledge & technology augmentation for innovation and entrepreneurship. These areas are on the priority in their development agenda as they are critical for advancement. Developing countries are always in search of new inventions which are going on around the globe and try to innovate indigenously that can be adapted to their local conditions.

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Majority of them now focus on trying to create conditions in which entrepreneurship and innovation lead to socioeconomic development. The importance of entrepreneurship in creating employment opportunities, innovative products/services and the formation of new business firms is seen as the engine of economic growth and progress (Lalkaka and Abetti, 1999; Khalil and Oiafen, 2010; Audretsch et al., 2016). Developing countries realised the potential of startups, started implementing policies to encourage entrepreneurs by offering financial and non-financial incentives through a variety of sources (Lalkaka and Abetti, 1999). These initiatives support the startup culture and assist small and medium-sized businesses in acquiring cutting-edge equipment and management techniques.

Back in 1960s, first incubator was established in the United States back in the 1960s to stimulate innovation and encourage entrepreneurship (Lewis, 2003). By providing infrastructure and other support services, business incubation, a sub-discipline of entrepreneurship, aids in the development of new businesses, their early survival, sustainment, achievement of growth, and improvement of the chances of progress in nascent years (Bergek and Norman 2008; Ramussen 2011). Business incubators are now viewed as an effective platform by the authorities and decision-makers at various levels for fostering innovation-led economic growth. In emerging countries, Incubators can significantly benefit entrepreneurs by increasing human capital and developing their networking (Abdelgawad, 2022). Additionally, business incubators' significant role in the formation of new technology-based growth enterprises has set the ball rolling across nations. The aim of incubator is to facilitate the entrepreneurial team with various tangible and intangible resources in the development of a new company (Churchill and Lewis, 1983; Birley, 1986; Pals, 2006; Nair and Blomquist, 2019; Al Sharif, 2022; Mohan and Chinchwadkar, 2022). In order to achieve this, they offer their services and participate in endeavours that aid in the creation of high-tech startups with a scalable business model.

By using a business incubation mechanism, which offers specialised services like shared office space, business counseling, and knowledge sharing, new firms are nurtured and closely watched in the early stages of growth (Birch, 1979; Gissy, 1984; Allen and Rahman, 1985; Deyanova et al., 2022). It is crucial to determine the success elements for effective incubation. Management doyen Peter Drucker once said "*you can't improve what you don't measure*". In the context of business incubation, it has become imperative to measure the performance of the incubators because they are either publicly funded or financed by non-

government/private agencies. This study tried to develop and refine a research instrument comprising antecedents and measures of Business incubator performance.

2. Literature Review

An elaborative and orderly literature related to business incubation was keenly reviewed by various authors such as Allen and Rahman (1985), Mian (1996), Hackett and Dilts (2004,) Theorakopoulos *et al.* (2014) in order to provide a systematic platform for entrepreneurial activities by doing a critical assessment of business incubation.

Despite the consistent definition of a business incubator, it converges three dimensions as business incubation model itself, its very purpose and the support services it provides to startups (Ayyash *et al.*, 2020). As stated in the description of business incubators, these organisations assist entrepreneurs in combining their concepts into a cohesive whole and sustaining business by mentoring and guiding them from the starting so that the new venture can transform into a growing and a successful business enterprise (NBIA 2010).

Business incubators become an essential policy tool for promoting the growth and development of entrepreneurship and business start-ups. Through its external networks, business incubators assist tenant companies in generating entrepreneurial value (Nair and Blomquist, 2019). The focus of incubator is to provide an environment to enhance the survival rate followed by scaling up of newly launched businesses by offering a method for identifying companies that are constrained by a lack of resources and managerial assistance (Ayatse *et al.*, 2017; Pattanasak, 2022). It includes the provision of facilities ranging from physical infrastructure, guidance and mentorship, seed capital to expertise for optimal utilization of creativity and the ability to market the entrepreneurial idea (Gandhi *et al.*, 2021). After reviewing the relevant literature, it has been inferred that the purpose of an incubator is to nurture the nascent ventures. In order to achieve the same it needs various inputs such as infrastructure, financial resources and managerial staff.

The researchers find it critical for the policies regarding selection should be positively connected with the achievement of their (business incubators) goals (Hackett and Dilts, 2004; Totterman and Sten, 2005). Therefore, tenant startup firms should disclose correct details regarding their proposed business and company while seeking admission in the business incubator (Pals, 2006). It was

also ascertained through literature that business incubators should implement a stringent selection process. With regard to the selection process, it is also mentioned that those who are ambitious should be given preference during selection for admission to a business incubator (Dvoulety et al., 2018). In this context, the stages of business development become important to mention. There are four stages of business development such as the idea stage, the attempt stage followed by the development stage, and finally the commercialization stage (Bricks, 1986). This study also sheds light on the relationship between conception of an idea & its implementation, where smaller the gap between two, greater the likelihood of establishing a new enterprise. Because of this, incubation aims to minimise the gap between these two stages and inspire independence by providing new business ideas. By offering them a variety of services, such as working space, business support and professional networking, business incubators are removing the factors that causes to failure for new and small businesses.

A business incubator/incubation center thus tries to offer proper services and structure to the tenant firms by sometimes managing their affairs partially and assisting in new venture creation (Smilor, 1987; Lalkaka and Abetti, 1999; Aernoudt, 2004; Chan and Lau, 2005; Gozali, 2020). The major components of business incubators often enumerated and studies in earlier research are as follows:

- Physical Infrastructure and shared office space
- Common services to tenant firms for controlling expenses
- Mentoring and Professional supervision
- Financial Support and Marketing assistance
- Networking with other stakeholders

Thus, it can be concluded that business incubators provided support in introduction new startups as well as strengthen them in their formative years when the chances of their failure are higher than survival. The business incubator helps new ventures and provides them the goodwill in view of stakeholders as well as its clients (Yannopoulos, 2017; Leitao, 2020). There are various kinds of incubators and the functions/role of these incubators depends upon the type to which they belong.

3. Research Methodology and Design

3.1. Objectives

Based on reviewed literature on business incubation, it is tried to establish the relationship between existing exogenous factors such as university linkages, infrastructural facilities, and networking and their relationship with endogenous variables i.e. business incubation performance, is the goal of evaluating the research.

3.2. Sample Frame

Through literature review a conceptual model has been developed (Refer to Figure 01) for measuring the performance of factors which leads to the success of for incubation centers. This is a pilot study to further develop and refine the measurement scale for performance assessment of business incubators, which is based on primary data collected from managers of thirty-two business incubators. Joreskog and Sorbom (1993) devised a formula for sample size determination for estimating structural models as follows:

$$K(K-1)/2, \text{ where } K = \text{no of variables under study}$$

For this pilot study, a sample size of 6 is required for the four variables, but this study carried out on 32 samples. Pilot surveys are primarily conducted for feasibility instead of hypothesis testing. Studies show that for conducting a pilot study, data collected from 20 respondents is sufficient (Birkett and Day, 1994) and even it can be 30 or in the range of 20 to 40 respondents would serve the purpose (Browne, 1995; Kieser and Wassemer, 1996; Julious, 2005). The sampling is Judgmental as the responses were collected from business incubation units. The collected data is analyzed and with the aid of SPSS 20.0® and Lisrel 9.00 software, measurement model has also been assessed.

3.3. Research Constructs and Conceptual Relationships

Researchers argued that the basis for measuring the success of a business incubator is different in every country i.e. it is not a universally accepted criterion (Phan et al., 2005). Some indicators such as the formation of a network and, support of financial institutions for tenant capitalization are important measures of performance (Campbell and Allen, 1987). The sustainability and growth of the incubator itself and the tendency to provide services are the mean indicators of incubator performance (Mian, 1997).

As far as India as a developing nation is concerned, it's on a growth and development path and at this very stage, significance of business incubators becomes pivotal, therefore is included in the government's economic strategy post-2000s. As a result, the current study aims to pinpoint the key success elements influencing incubator outcomes and suggest strategies for improving business incubator performance. This study looks into how connections to universities, infrastructure, and networking might improve the performance of business incubators.

a) University Linkages

Business incubators linked with academia emphasizes on innovation and growth. Universities are redefining themselves as an entrepreneurial educational hub. Credit goes to their well-developed infrastructure, presence of expert faculty members, access to various databases through libraries, laboratories for R&D, and alumni connect. Business incubation centres are important for fostering an entrepreneurial culture among students and growing entrepreneurship in a nation, in addition to providing entrepreneurial education and training (Mian, 1997; Grimaldi and Grandi, 2005; Aerts et al., 2007; Pauwels et al., 2016). Studies emphasize on university linkage and advocates that this construct plays an important role as far as the performance of business incubator is concerned. It is also argued that the type of business incubator depends upon the country in which it is operating and most of the incubators act as research centres under the influence of the university. The incubators in developing nations are either government-funded or foreign-country-funded (Koshi, 2011). The performance and behaviour of business incubators are influenced by interaction among academia, industry, and government in a knowledge-based economy (Etzkowitz, 2009).

b) Incubation Facilities

The incubation facilities are the set of tangibles provided to the tenant firm like physical space, shared offices, laboratories for R&D for developing prototypes, and access to databases for patent search etc. before starting a business. Studies put emphasis on the role of size on the influence of incubation facilities in order to enhance the performance of business incubators. The facilities include preparation of business plan, development & testing of prototype and further product improvement, financial assistance, and soft skill training to incubates (Mavuri et al. 2020). These facilities are of immense importance at different incubation phase. In the pre-incubation phase when the business incubators

are facilitating new business plans, knowledge-intensive business techniques are being provided. In the incubation phase financial services and business development services are being provided and in post incubation stage a business incubator extends its support to the firms successfully graduated from the business incubator (Fernandez et al., 2015).

C) Networking

Another important construct behind success of any business incubator is a network with the different agencies for knowledge sharing, obtaining finance and smooth operations, stems from the network theory (Nohria and Eccles, 1992). This theory advocates the idea that the main role of an incubator is to channelize the technical know-how to its clients and find out ways to commercialize the innovations. The use of networks for the enhancement of the performance of business incubator/incubation centres is well mentioned in several studies and considered that networking can be used as a major strategy to benefit both incubator and incubatee (Akcomak, 2009). Like other incubator facilities, networking facilities also helps business incubator/incubation center in different stages of the incubation process and the exploitation of networks acts as a critical success factor for any business incubator (McCann, Reuer and Lahiri, 2016). Networking can be made efficient both internally as well as externally, the robustness of internal networks enhances the competitiveness of a business incubator (Hughes, Ireland and Morgan, 2007; Leitão, 2022) on the other hand the robustness of external factors encourage entrepreneurs in getting and procuring many important resources needed to survive in the market (Eveleens, van Rijnsoever and Niesten, 2017).

d) Business Incubator Performance

Till date, there is no consensus on the definition and the way to measure business incubator performance but many researchers show interest in this area. Few studies tried to define and assess the performance of business incubators (Ayatse, Kwahar, and Iyortsuun, 2017; Eveleens, vanRijnsoever and Niesten, 2017; Gozali, 2020; Pattanasak, 2022). We have to consider some definitions of the performance of a business incubator for developing a conceptual model as the performance is generally considered as the objective attainment activity vis-à-vis its expected outcome (Mosselman and Prince, 2004). So, it is important to highlight that the objective of a business incubator should be centered on the clients' successful graduation in order to accommodate new admissions.

The number of successful graduates is therefore regarded as a sign of a constructive incubation process. Survival rate and graduation rate become significant when evaluating the effectiveness of a business incubator. In a similar view, business incubators are renowned for producing jobs (Brooks, 1986; Al-Mubarak and Busler, 2010). Consequently, an incubator should foster an inventive culture and provide support for technology transfer (Mian, 1997; Phillips, 2002). Studies also argued that business incubators are crucial in the development of industry clusters and economic growth (Hansen et al. 2000; Fukugawa, 2013). The items pertaining to all these sub-constructs can be added to the scale while measuring the performance of a business incubator.

3.3. Conceptual Model of Research

A Conceptual model should have both independent and dependent variables (Anderson & Gerbing, 1991). The model specification of present study is as follows:

$$\text{BIP} = f \{ \text{UL}, \text{NG}, \text{IF} \}$$

BIP = Business Incubator Performance (Endogenous/Dependent variable).

UL = University linkage (Exogenous/Independent variable).

IF = Incubator Facilities (Exogenous/Independent variable).

NG = Networking (Exogenous/Independent variable).

Figure-1 : Conceptual Model for Study Constructs

Source : Author's Contribution.

3.4. Respondents Profile

The data for this pilot study has been collected through a sample of 32 respondents, in which 56.2 percent of the sample of 32 people were women, 75.4 percent were single, and 20.8% of people were married, and the average age was 30. Regarding education levels, 14.1 percent finished higher education, while the highest level of education held by 10% of those was a postgraduate degree. We created the first goal of the article to validate the components utilized by factorial confirmatory analysis once we knew the profile of the respondents.

4. Analysis, Results and Discussion

Response Bias and Non-Response Bias Assessment

Before beginning the data analysis, the data's response and non-response bias were evaluated.

Response Bias Assessment

Response bias can steer participant replies in self-reporting research away from the ideal response. Additionally, it undermines the survey instrument's validity (Hair et al, 2012).

Non-Response Bias

This bias developed as a result of some respondents responding slowly or not at all. To examine the differences between respondents (early) and late or non-responders, independent sample t-tests can be used. If no differences were found, as stated by (Malhotra, 2012), response bias does not exist.

Table-1 : Group Statistics for Estimation of Non-Response Bias.

	Constructs	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
UL	Early	12	2.4425	1.22250	0.22173
	Late	20	2.0625	1.22269	0.22110
NG	Early	12	2.8626	1.345260	0.24102
	Late	20	1.2521	1.4251	0.25197
IF	Early	12	2.6324	1.4282	0.25123
	Late	20	1.7027	1.4258	0.26118
BIP	Early	12	1.6425	1.3250	0.27173
	Late	20	2.1625	1.3269	0.25110

Source : Field Study.

To assess the normality of data in Table-2, a z-test is applied to test normality, using skewness and kurtosis. A Z score can be obtained by dividing the skewness values or excess kurtosis values by their standard errors. Z value of ± 1.96 and absolute z value of ± 3.29 are sufficient to establish the normality of data in case of small sample ($n < 50$) and medium sized sample ($50 < n < 300$) respectively. In this research, the Z statistic is greater than 3.50 for all research parameters ensuring the normality of the data.

Table-2 : A Z score for Testing Normality

Construct	Mean	Std. Deviation	Z Value
UL	4.566	1.34	4.45
NG	5.434	1.08	3.89
IF	4.555	1.56	5.76
BIP	4.098	1.24	6.04

Source : Field Study.

Assessment of Unidimensionality, Reliability and Validity

The magnitude of the factorial load must also be observed in CFA, and variables with low loadings should be eliminated from the model. Cronbach's alpha (Cronbach, 1951) was used to assess the construct's dependability, with values greater than 0.7 being acceptable. By analyzing standardized residuals, it is possible to confirm the construct's unidimensionality. The results for CFA are shown in Figure-2.

Convergent validity was also established through independent t-tests. The values for all the scales were above recommended 1.96. The results are shown in Figure-3.

Figure-2 : CFA for All Study Scales

Figure-3 : t Values to Establish Convergent Validity

Table-3 : Cronbach Alpha, Construct Reliability, and Variance Extracted for exogenous variables

Construct	Cronbach Alpha	Construct Reliability	Variance Extracted
UL	.77	.79	.46
NG	.84	.96	.80
IF	.88	.89	.67
BIP	.85	.85	.55

Source : Field Study.

The above Table-3 shows different values of Cronbach Alpha, Construct Reliability, and Variance Extracted for exogenous variables such as University Linkages, networking and incubator facilities provided for incubatee firms as well as for endogenous variable i.e. Business Incubator Performance. In Cronbach's Alpha if value of 0.7 or higher is found the items are considered sufficiently consistent to measure the reliability, which indicates responses are consistent between items.

5. Conclusion

This study is useful for further investigation on the condition of incubators right now and what initiatives are required for the advancement of business incubators in the future. The research instrument is established from the comprehensive literature review and measures are identified as university linkages, networking, and incubator facilities that impact the Incubator performance. Only a conceptual model is developed in this pilot study from data which is obtained from thirty-two incubation managers. It can be empirically tested in future research by conducting a quantitative survey of a subset of Indian BIs. Through this data the research scale was refined and testing required for the assessment of the measurement model was performed. Initially, CFA was performed and all the scales were found unidimensional. Further, tests of validity and reliability were also performed, where the scale was found valid and reliable. The existing research serves as a foundation and identifies relationships that could be enhanced and reinforced by a cross-sectional/longitudinal or even a case-based analysis of business incubators' best practices. Therefore, we propose that this scale can be used for further research and the findings obtained can be generalized.

References

- Aernoudt, R. (2004). Incubators: tool for entrepreneurship?. *Small business economics*, 23(2), 127-135.
- Akçomak, Ý. S. (2011). Incubators as tools for entrepreneurship promotion in developing countries. *Entrepreneurship, innovation, and economic development*, 228-264.
- Al Sharif, R., Pokharel, S., Ayari, M. A., Essam, M., & Aqeel, S. (2022). Enabling Open Innovation in Digital Startups through the Incubation Program - A Case of Qatar. *Sustainability*, 14(11), 6557.
- Al-Mubarak, H. M., & Busler, M. (2012). The incubators economic indicators: Mixed approaches. *Journal of Case Research in Business and Economics*, 4, 1.
- Allen, D. N., & Rahman, S. (1985). Small business incubators: a positive environment for entrepreneurship. *Journal of Small Business Management (pre-1986)*, 23(000003), 12.
- Al Ayyash, S., McAdam, M., & O'Gorman, C. (2020). Towards a new perspective on the heterogeneity of business incubator-incubation definitions. *IEEE transactions on engineering management*, 69(4), 1738-1752.
- Aly Abdelgawad, A. (2022). Incubate the Emerging: The Role of Incubators in Emerging Countries (Dissertation). Retrieved from <http://urn.kb.se/resolve?urn=urn:nbn:se:uu:diva-482549>
- Ayatse, F. A., Kwahar, N., & Iyortsuun, A. S. (2017). Business incubation process and firm performance: an empirical review. *Journal of Global Entrepreneurship Research*, 7(1), 1-17.
- Azadnia, A. H., Stephens, S., Ghadimi, P., & Onofrei, G. (2022). A comprehensive performance measurement framework for business incubation centres: Empirical evidence in an Irish context. *Business Strategy and the Environment*, 31(5), 2437-2455.
- Benedetti, M. H., & Torkomian, A. L. V. (2011). Uma análise da influência da cooperação Universidade-Empresas sobre inovação tecnológica. *Gestão & Produção*, 18, 145-158.
- Bergek, A., & Norrman, C. (2008). Incubator best practice: A framework. *Technovation*, 28(1-2), 20-28.
- Birkett, M. A., & Day, S. J. (1994). Internal pilot studies for estimating sample size. *Statistics in medicine*, 13(2324), 2455-2463.
- Birley, S. (1986). The role of new firms: Births, deaths and job generation. *Strategic Management Journal*, 7(4), 361-376.

- Brooks, O. J. (1986). Economic development through entrepreneurship: incubators and the incubation process. *Economic Development Review*, 4(2), 24-29.
- Browne, R. H. (1995). On the use of a pilot sample for sample size determination. *Statistics in medicine*, 14(17), 1933-1940.
- Campbell, C., & Allen, D. N. (1987). The small business incubator industry: micro-level economic development. *Economic Development Quarterly*, 1(2), 178-191.
- Chan, K. F., & Lau, T. (2005). Assessing technology incubator programs in the science park: the good, the bad and the ugly. *Technovation*, 25(10), 1215-1228.
- Collinson, S., & Gregson, G. (2003). Knowledge networks for new technology-based firms: an international comparison of local entrepreneurship promotion. *R&D Management*, 33(2), 189-208.
- Dvouletý, O., Longo, M. C., Blažková, I., Lukeš, M., & Andera, M. (2018). Are publicly funded Czech incubators effective? The comparison of performance of supported and non-supported firms. *European Journal of Innovation Management*, 21 (4), 543–563.
- Etzkowitz, H., & Marina, R. (2009). Hélicetriplice. *Universidade-indústria-governo: inovaçãoem movimento*. Porto Alegre: EDIPUCRS.
- Eveleens, C. P., van Rijnsoever, F. J., & Niesten, E. M. (2017). How network-based incubation helps start-up performance: a systematic review against the background of management theories. *The Journal of Technology Transfer*, 42(3), 676-713.
- Fernández Fernández, M. T., Blanco Jiménez, F. J., & Cuadrado Roura, J. R. (2015). Business incubation: innovative services in an entrepreneurship ecosystem. *The Service Industries Journal*, 35(14), 783-800.
- Gandhi, V., Syed, A. A., & Kumar, S. (2021). A study of performance indicators of Technology Business Incubators (TBIs) in India. *Management Dynamics*, 21(1), 14-23.
- Hair, J. F., Jr.; Hult, G. T. M.; Ringle, C.; Sarstedt, M. A Primer on Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM); Sage Publications: Beverly Hills, CA, USA, 2012.
- Hackett, S. M., & Dilts, D. M. (2004). A systematic review of business incubation research. *The Journal of Technology Transfer*, 29(1), 55-82.
- Hackett, S. M., & Dilts, D. M. (2008). Inside the black box of business incubation: Study B-scale assessment, model refinement, and incubation outcomes. *The Journal of Technology Transfer*, 33(5), 439-471.

- Hansen, M. T., Chesbrough, H. W., Nohria, N., & Sull, D. N. (2000). Networked incubators. Hothouses of the new economy. *Harvard Business Review*, 78(5), 74–199.
- Hong, J., Yang, Y., Wang, H., Zhou, Y., & Deng, P. (2019). Incubator interdependence and incubation performance in China's transition economy: the moderating roles of incubator ownership and strategy. *Technology Analysis & Strategic Management*, 31(1), 96-110.
- Hughes, M., Ireland, R. D., & Morgan, R. E. (2007). Stimulating dynamic value: Social capital and business incubation as a pathway to competitive success. *Long Range Planning*, 40(2), 154-177.
- Jöreskog, K. G., & Sörbom, D. (1993). *LISREL 8: Structural equation modeling with the SIMPLIS command language*. Scientific software international.
- Julious, S. A. (2005). Sample size of 12 per group rule of thumb for a pilot study. *Pharmaceutical Statistics: The Journal of Applied Statistics in the Pharmaceutical Industry*, 4(4), 287-291.
- Khalil, M. A., & Olafsen, E. (2010). Enabling innovative entrepreneurship through business incubation. In *The Innovation for Development Report 2009–2010* (pp. 69-84). Palgrave Macmillan, London.
- Kiran, R., & Bose, S. C. (2020). Stimulating business incubation performance: Role of networking, university linkage and facilities. *Technology Analysis & Strategic Management*, 32(12), 1407-1421.
- Kieser, M., & Wassmer, G. (1996). On the use of the upper confidence limit for the variance from a pilot sample for sample size determination. *Biometrical journal*, 38(8), 941-949.
- Koshy, P. (2011). Role of Rural Business Incubators in Translating Micro Finance to Sustainable Micro Enterprises. *International NGO Journal*, 6(4), 104–112.
- Lalkaka, R. (1996). Technology business incubators: critical determinants of success. *Annals of the New York Academy of Sciences*, 798(1), 270-290.
- Lalkaka, R. (2002). Technology business incubators to help build an innovation-based economy. *Journal of Change Management*, 3(2), 167-176.
- Lalkaka, R., & Abetti, P. (1999). Business incubation and enterprise support systems in restructuring countries. *Creativity and innovation management*, 8(3), 197-209.
- Lalkaka, R., & J. Bishop (1996). *Business Incubators in Economic Development - An Initial Assessment in Industrialising Countries*. United Nations Development Programme, New York.

- Leitão, J., Pereira, D., & Gonçalves, Â. (2022). Business Incubators, Accelerators, and Performance of Technology-Based Ventures: A Systematic Literature Review. *Journal of Open Innovation: Technology, Market, and Complexity*, 8(1), 46.
- Lewis, V. L., & Churchill, N. C. (1983). The five stages of small business growth. *Harvard Business Review* 61 (1), 30–50
- Malhotra, N. K. *Marketing Research: An Applied Orientation*; Pearson Education: New Delhi, India, 2012.
- Mavuri, S., Chavali, K., & Vadakkiveetil, A. K. (2023). Role of Incubation Centers in Promoting Sustainable Development in Nigeria.
- McAdam, M., & McAdam, R. (2008). High tech start-ups in University Science Park incubators: The relationship between the start-up's lifecycle progression and use of the incubator's resources. *Technovation*, 28(5), 277-290.
- McCann, B. T., Reuer, J. J., & Lahiri, N. (2016). Agglomeration and the choice between acquisitions and alliances: An information economics perspective. *Strategic Management Journal*, 37(6), 1085-1106.
- Mian, S. A. (1997). Assessing and managing the university technology business incubator: an integrative framework. *Journal of Business Venturing*, 12(4), 251-285.
- Mian, S. (2013). Business incubation and incubation mechanisms chapter. *Handbook on entrepreneurship research: What we know and what we need to know*, 335-366.
- Mohan, V., & Chinchwadkar, R. (2022). Technology Business Incubation: A Literature Review and Gaps. *International Journal of Global Business and Competitiveness*, 17(1), 53-63.
- Mosselman, M., & Prince, Y. (2004). Review of methods to measure the effectiveness of state aid to SMEs. *Zoetermeer: EIM*.
- National Business Incubation Association (NBIA), (2010).
- Nair, S., & Blomquist, T. (2019). Failure prevention and management in business incubation: practices towards a scalable business model. *Technology Analysis & Strategic Management*, 31(3), 266-278.
- Nohria, N., and R. G. Eccles. (1992). *Networks and Organization*. Harvard Business School Press.
- Pals, S. (2006). Factors determining success/failure in business incubators: A literature review of 17 countries. *Worcester Polytechnic Institute*, 2-81.

- Phan, P. H., Siegel, D. S., & Wright, M. (2005). Science parks and incubators: observations, synthesis and future research. *Journal of business venturing*, 20(2), 165-182.
- Pattanasak, P., Anantana, T., Paphawasit, B., & Wudhikarn, R. (2022). Critical Factors and Performance Measurement of Business Incubators: A Systematic Literature Review. *Sustainability*, 14(8), 4610.
- Phillips, R. G. (2002). Technology business incubators: how effective as technology transfer mechanisms?. *Technology in society*, 24(3), 299-316.
- Salamzadeh, Y., Sangosanya, T. A., Salamzadeh, A., & Braga, V. (2022). Entrepreneurial universities and social capital: The moderating role of entrepreneurial intention in the Malaysian context. *The International Journal of Management Education*, 20(1), 100609.
- Sharma, S., & Vohra, N. (2021). Indian business incubation ecosystem: a multilevel analysis. In *Handbook of Research on Business and Technology Incubation and Acceleration* (pp. 260-279). Edward Elgar Publishing.
- Smilor, R. W. (1987). Managing the incubator system: critical success factors to accelerate new company development. *IEEE Transactions on Engineering Management*, (3), 146-155.
- Sohail, K., Belitski, M., & Christiansen, L. C. (2023). Developing business incubation process frameworks: A systematic literature review. *Journal of Business Research*, 162, 113902.
- Theodorakopoulos, N., Kakabadse, N. K., & McGowan, C. (2014). What matters in business incubation? A literature review and a suggestion for situated theorising. *Journal of small business and enterprise development*, 21 (4), 602-622.
- Tötterman, H., & Sten, J. (2005). Start-ups: Business incubation and social capital. *International Small Business Journal*, 23(5), 487-511.
- Yannopoulos, P. (2017). Business Strategies for Small Firms and New Ventures. *World Review of Business Research*, 7(1), 58-68.